

INTRODUCTION OF MODERN PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN MEDICINE TO THE SCIENCE OF BIOPHYSICS

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Abstract: This thesis presents information about the current rapid growth of information in the field of science and technology, the limited time available to adequately use it in the process of teaching biophysics in medical fields, and advanced pedagogical technologies in the education system, which aim to prepare young students as mature and well-rounded individuals.

Keywords: physics, medicine, pedagogical technologies, biophysics, solids.

Aim: At the stage of development of our country in the field of science and technology, the information is growing rapidly and the time for its adequate use in the teaching process is limited, and the time has come to introduce advanced pedagogical technologies into the education system, which aims to prepare young students as mature and well-rounded individuals. It is a pity that until now, traditional teaching methods continue in educational institutions and due to the lack of use of pedagogical technology elements in teaching, students have become passive listeners of lectures. It was concluded that the goals and tasks of the education system are not being adequately implemented due to the inability of the teacher to organize lessons correctly, the lack of student and teacher cooperation in the lesson process, the inability to fully and partially use various methods and techniques consisting of elements of advanced pedagogical technology, and the limitation of the information in the textbook on the new topic being organized.

Result: Therefore, when the lesson is conducted in a traditional way, there is not enough opportunity for students to think independently, the teacher conveys the material given in the textbook to the student in the form of a lecture and it is difficult to determine to what extent the students have learned new knowledge during the lesson, as a result, there is no way to know whether the lesson was conducted effectively or ineffectively. That is, the student listens to the teacher's lecture boringly or is distracted by other thoughts without listening. As a result, the goal of the lesson is not achieved and time is wasted.

The use of non-traditional educational forms and methods in teaching physics gives positive results. When choosing one or another method, students should be guided to think freely in all aspects, become creative active participants, and use a variety of methods, for example, discussion lessons, creative research, and independent work. Students have the opportunity to freely express their views and opinions without taking a one-sided approach to the issue. Lessons organized in the same way, solving problems in the same way, bore the student, as a result, the student becomes a passive listener and the goal of the lesson is not achieved. Therefore, it is important to provide knowledge in the lesson using advanced pedagogical and information technologies in an appropriate manner. As an example, the methodology for teaching the topics, depending on the level of complexity, is given as follows: 1. A complex topic in terms of content: Kinetic energy of rotational motion of solid bodies. 2. A topic of medium complexity in terms of content: Kinetic energy of reciprocating motion. 3. A topic that is not complex in content: Energy of interaction of bodies. The situations in which these topics are manifested in the lesson process, as well as the form, methods and means, are determined.

Therefore, if the educational process is planned in advance, the educational goal is clearly set, students' joint decision-making, the correct assignment of tasks, the use of visual aids, the accurate, convincing and scientific presentation of educational material, the fair assessment of student knowledge, the effective and timely use of pedagogical technology elements will yield effective results.

The use of advanced pedagogical technologies in the process of physics education is of great importance due to the fact that it ensures the exchange of roles between the subjects of this process - teachers and students. According to the leading ideological orientation of traditional education, the teacher has been performing a leadership role during the lesson and has been monitoring and evaluating student activity based on his orders, while according to the ideological orientation of the theory of pedagogical technology, his role in the educational process is to guide students, give advice where necessary, suggest educational tasks and indirectly guide the general process.

Conclusion: A new approach to organizing the educational process serves to ensure the student's absolute priority of activity. Now he has the opportunity to receive mainly independent education, to think independently about the topic proposed for his organization and the idea put forward in it, to share his thoughts with his peers on the formulation of the problem expressed in the solution of the topic.

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